

Real-time lodging analysis for smart combine harvester

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Abstract

In this project, we tried to develop technology to estimate yield by grasping lodging condition during harvesting operation using image processing. The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between degree of lodging and number of grain for estimating yield variability within a field.

100 Grain sample data was obtained from 18 fields (5.4ha). Lodging level was defined as 5 steps (i.e. level 1: 15, 2:30, 3:45, 4:60 and 5:75 degree, respectively). This study measured ground truth of whole kernels, brown rice weight and weight of waste, respectively. The result of observation indicated that weight of clean hulled rice at level 5 was 1.05 times larger than level 1. However waste rice at level 5 was 3.08 times as much as level 1. Level 1 tended to have higher percentage of ripened grains than that of level 5. The average N content and weight of winnowed rough of level 1 were 0.72% and 753.1kg/10a, level 5 of them were 0.79% and 832.7kg/10a, respectively. In addition, harvest time under level 5 condition was 2 times longer than level 1. The mention above, creating a lodging map during harvesting season would be important factor for strategy making of lodging prevention for future crop management.

Introduction

There is concern that agricultural productivity will decline because lack of successor, progress of aging, and increase of abandoned farmland (Tashiro, 1999). In 2015, the percentage of producers under 50 in Japan is only 12% from the total agricultural population (MAFF, 2015). Technical management succession is one of the most significant issues in agricultural production. This research aimed to increase utilization efficiency of combine harvester. The information on harvest such as yield and moisture is important factor in harvesting of grain such as rice and wheat. This information is the result of crop management following year. Yield maps provide feedback information on how crops respond to certain soil and crop management practices and are used to determine recommendation rates for many inputs (Dingemans, 1997; Birrell et al. 1996). Moreover, precision farming in paddies has many possibilities for new cropping system (Chosa et al. 2012).

On the other hand, harvested efficiency is important for growers to consider crop conditions and weather. Because it is difficult to get the objective information about the yield and moisture of each field. Therefore, more accurate mapping technology is necessary (Makino et al. 2007).

So far, as a technique of grain yield mapping, Arslan et al. (2002) studied grain yield-mapping in combine harvester using yield data and location data. Makino et al. (2007) developed a head-feeding combine harvester capable of measuring, displaying and recording yield and moisture while harvesting. In addition, Hayashi (2007) developed a geographic information system (GIS) for collecting farming information.

They decided the time from harvesting to tank discharge and proposed a method to solve the time-lag of combine harvester by setting tailing return. Solving the issue of tailing return is required in order to do highly accurate yield mapping using head-feeding combine harvester.

We focused on degree of lodging at harvest time an alternative of yield. It depends on completion of extension of spikes up to heading stage and too much N and lack of sunshine make lodging large. A relationship between lodging and these are few after the heading stage (Seko, 1962). Also, excessive N application in paddies leads to lodging and decreased grain quality (Makino et al. 2007). We estimated that rough estimates of yield were possible by looking at the degree of lodging.

In introducing this system to combine harvester, we are studying development of a system which can automatically judge the degree of lodging by using deep learning. Therefore, we also developed a system that can perform automatic determination in real time lodging using deep learning and training data.

The objectives of this research are 1) to elucidate a relationship between degree of lodging and number of grain, 2) to elucidate whether yield can be estimated by looking at lodging, 3) to create a lodging map by applying these data, 4) to confirm whether it can be used as cultivation management guideline for the next year, and 5) to judge degree of lodging using deep learning.

Materials and methods

Experiment were conducted in 2016 at the paddy fields of Takemoto Farm (36.43°N, 136.50°E).

1. Lodging of paddy rice

The sampling strategy was that 20 Grain sample data for each degree of lodging was obtained from 18 fields (5.4ha) at September 6 to 9. Lodging level was defined as 5 steps (Figure 1, i.e. level 1:15, 2:30, 3:45, 4:60 and 5:75 degree, respectively).

Figure 1. Degree of lodging of paddy

After sampling, threshing and proceeding were performed as the thresher (OMM, Ohyatanzo), the rice huller (25M, Ohyatanzo) and the winnower (PS, Ohyatanzo). Then the rice grader (TW SB, Satake) Weight of the whole tops, whole kernels and brown rice and moisture were measured at October 24.

2. Lodging map

The tablet (FZ-M1, Panasonic) and the head-feeding combine harvester (HJ6123GZCAPLW, ISEKI) were used in this experiment. The tablet was fixed to the combine harvester as shown in Figure 2 (Height 1.5m, Depression 17°). Images of rice just before harvesting were taken by the tablet's camera and the speed of the combine harvester was 0.5-1.5m/s. Using this method, 156870 images were obtained. The degree of lodging was determined according to aforementioned steps (Figure 3) and we investigated whether it can be applied to the lodging map using Farm activity record management system (FARMS).

Figure 2. Position of tablet

Lodging level 2

Lodging level 4

Figure 3. To determine the degree of lodging visually

3. Farm activity record management system (FARMS)

Farm activity record management system (FARMS) is a georeferenced information system that consists of a main program running on a standalone PC, which browses and stores data logger interface (Hayashi, 2014). The powerful analytical capabilities of this device allow the examination of farm conditions and precisely monitor the influence of farm management practices.

4. Deep learning

As the training data, 156870 images used in the aforementioned lodging map was used. In this experiment, the lodging basis was set to 4 to 5 in the degree of lodging. Histogram of Gradient (HOG) was applied to sample images. The direction of the edge was calculated based on the x- and y-directions for each pixel, and the local feature amount was obtained. The cell size was 30 x 30, number of cells was 16 x 16, and the direction of all the pixels in the cell was quantized in nine directions. Bag of Visual Words (BoVW) feature amount was based on K-means clustering.

For identification, HOG and BoVW were applied like learning. The number of cells input to each cluster is totalized according to the obtained division, and the number of cells of each cluster is connected in series to create K-dimensional image feature amount. Then lodging was judged based on the linear Support Vector Machine learned in advance in the space of the image feature amount.

Results and discussions

1. Between lodging and each component

Table 1 showed relationship between degree of lodging and measured components. The yield of the lodging level 5 was higher than 1 from this Table. Correspondingly, weight of rice screenings tends to increase, too. From the result, level 5 would have bigger profit because of higher yield. But since cleaning is performed after grain-drying, energy is also used for rice screenings. Hence, extra energy is required, and as a result there are cases where there is no significant change in profit.

Table 1. Average weight per 10a for each degree of lodging (kg)

lodging level	whole tops	whole kernels	rough brown rice	clean brown rice	correction of moisture 15%	rice screenings
1	1,534.4	753.1	612.8	596.9	590.6	15.8
2	1,403.7	717.5	586.9	570.3	565.7	16.4
3	1,432.8	725.1	596.6	576.1	571.7	20.3
4	1,374.8	698.0	542.9	542.9	539.1	27.1
5	1,596.7	832.7	617.6	627.6	611.7	49.0

2. Lodging map

From this experiment, it was found that degree of lodging may be applicable to lodging map. The future challenge will be how to apply the lodging map and performed in order to create precise lodging map at harvest in cooperation with single-frequency RTK-GPS that can be mounted on tablet.

3. Deep learning

As a result of comparing the lodging prediction by this system with visual measurement of actual lodging condition, model accuracy is shown in Table 2. From this result, the average was 72.4%. Forthcoming challenges, it is necessary to judge with higher precision by increasing the sample image.

Table 2. Correct answer rate

correct answer rate (%)	number of image
50-60	2
60-70	3
70-80	4
80-90	2
90-100	1

Conclusions

This paper conducted the feasibility study to judge the degree of lodging using deep learning. Regarding the relationship between rice screening and degree of lodging, lodging level 5 has a higher yield than 2. Correspondingly, weight of rice screenings tend to increase, too. In the future, it is necessary to adjust the amount of N. In addition, as a result of deep learning using 156870 sample

images, it was possible to obtain a correct answer rate of 72.4%. Work on creating a lodging map using deep learning by cooperating with single-frequency RTK-GPS.

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